

Coherence Gradients in Adaptive Risk Estimation

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Abstract – Many sensing scenarios involve tradeoff between diverse sets of constraints that involve measuring and parameterizing some high dimensional sensing environment trade-space to give minimal estimation risk. Integrating and simplifying these tradeoffs is a daunting task, particularly in the context where the underlying assumptions of signal and noise distributions can result from complex statistical models and these models can evolve in time. Thus we need a strategy to reduce the complexity of the measurement process, parameterize the tradeoff space, and adapt to dynamic changes as the sensing scenarios evolve. We propose using coherence of the measurement process as a means of characterizing both the resource trade-space and the estimation process. We will use gradients in the coherence resource trade space to find the minimum estimator risk over some local sensing space and show how this process can adapt the process to global changes when they occur.

I. INTRODUCTION

We will first describe how coherence is used to characterize the resource trade-space in measuring some high dimensional sensing environment. We will then describe how we can relate both estimator bias and variance to coherence. We will then describe how coherence can parameterize our maximum likelihood estimation process and develop an expression for estimator risk. From this we will show how coherence can be used to find the minimum estimator risk in this context. We will then describe an algorithm to adapt to global changes in the risk estimation process as the sensing environment and resource trade space changes.

II. COHERENCE, MEASUREMENT, AND RESOURCE TRADE SPACE

Most measurement is reduced to something as follows. We have some signal envi-

ronment S and some interference environment E and we wish to measure these with some measurement vector Φ_Λ

$$X = \Phi_\Lambda \otimes (S + E) \quad (1)$$

The problem in most measurement scenarios is getting the right Φ_Λ to separate S from E . Recently there has been a lot of work in sparse approximation of signal and noise environments. This work has come in the context of compressed sensing. We can define our measurement process such that Φ_Λ consists of the individual waveform projections on the environment defined by $\phi_{i,i \in 1, \dots, N}$. The basic idea of sparse recovery algorithms such as compressive sensing is that we can then construct a recovery basis Ψ such that the correlation between sensing and recovery bases is minimal. The matrix product of our measurement basis with our recovery basis Ψ is our signal conditioning basis Ω where Ω_Λ and Φ_Λ represent the bases conditioned by the vectors in Ψ selected by p steps of our signal recovery algorithm.

$$\Omega_\Lambda = \Psi_\Lambda \Phi_\Lambda \quad (2)$$

We can form the channel covariance matrix $R_{XX} = E\{X, X\}$ of each sampled signal and define the inner product of our measurement and recovery basis with the variable Y as is shown in the following equation

$$Y = \langle \Psi, \Phi_\Lambda (S + E) \rangle \quad (3)$$

We will now review the basics of sparse approximation of compressive sensing [6] in the context of the previous discussion. Any signal in \mathcal{R}^M can be represented as a basis of $M \times 1$ vectors $\{\varphi_i\}_{i=1}^M$. Candes and Tau [6] show M corresponds to the sampling rate or bandwidth of our measurement waveform. If we assume the basis is orthonormal, we can form an $M \times M$ matrix by stacking the vectors $\Psi := [\varphi_1 | \varphi_2 | \dots | \varphi_N]$ where we form an $M \times 1$ column vec-

tor of weighting coefficients $y_i = \langle \psi_i, x_i \rangle = \psi_i^T x_i$ where T denotes Hermitian transpose. The purpose of sparse or compressed sensing is to represent x with a linear combination of just K basis vectors where $K \ll M$. Consider a linear measurement process that computes $M < N$ inner products between x and a collection of vectors $\{\phi_j\}_{j=1}^M$ as in $y_j = \langle \phi_j, x_j \rangle$. Stacking the measurements y_j into the $N \times 1$ vector y and the measurements vector ϕ_j^T as rows in $M \times N$ matrix Φ . Candes and Tau [4] also show that M corresponds to the number of measurements from separate distributed elements made on a signal. The parameterized covariance matrix is $C_{XX} = E\{\langle \Omega_\Lambda X, \Omega_\Lambda X \rangle\}$ and Ψ is the set of vectors that is selected to diagonalize C_{XX} . Thus our resource trade space can be parameterized by the bandwidth.

We can achieve guarantees of the recovery of our sparse matrix S in our noise environment E given that we meet certain requirements in our coherence parameter which will be described next. The if we assume our basis Ψ is orthogonal, algorithms such as Orthogonal Matching Pursuit algorithm basically seek to condition the matrix C_{XX} with the basis Ψ using a greed strategy to recover the signal S

$$X_{n+1} = X_n - \Omega_\Lambda(S + E) \quad (4)$$

Given its greedy nature Orthogonal Matching Pursuits [16] is an extremely efficient means of computing the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix C_{XX} as we shall see in the next section. Typical pseudo-inverse methods that use QR factorization can be up to order M^3 in complexity where $M \times M$ is the dimension of the covariance matrix whereas Orthogonal Matching Pursuit is typically order $M \log M$ in complexity. Additionally, Orthogonal Matching Pursuits, because it is an iterative method, can reduce the off diagonal terms in C_{XX} by a measured amount thereby allowing the user to set the amount of error in the inverse covariance matrix approximation. This approach has great advantages in correlated interference and ill posed inverse problems.

III. CONVERGENCE AND COHERENCE IN SPARSE SIGNAL RECOVERY

In order to establish how Orthogonal Matching Pursuits converges [12] in a noisy signal environment we now define the coherence between our measurement Φ and reconstruction basis Ψ . Basic coherence can be defined with

$$\mu_{i,j,i \neq j} = \frac{\langle \Psi_i, \Omega_j \rangle}{|\Psi_i| |\Omega_j|} \quad (5)$$

such that $0 \leq \mu_{ij} \leq 1$ which happens naturally without normalization if Ψ_i and Ω_i are each elements orthogonal bases. Gribonval defines cumulative coherence using a p^{th} order Babel function with the following expression of reconstruction atoms outside Λ with

$$\mu_p(\Phi, \Psi, \Lambda) = \sup_{l \notin \Lambda} \left(\sum_{j \in \Lambda} |\langle \phi_p, \psi_j \rangle|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (6)$$

This is our worst case coherence. We can also define the coherence of the atoms inside the support Λ with the follow expression

$$\mu_p^{in}(\Phi, \Psi, \Lambda) = \sup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_p(\Phi_\Lambda, \Psi_\Lambda, \Lambda \setminus \{i\}) \quad (7)$$

Waheed [1] defines coherence using and average value

$$\mu_{avg} = 1/n \sum_{i \neq j} \langle \Psi_i, \Omega_j \rangle \quad (8)$$

Thus we can have average coherence where \tilde{m} is defined by is the number frequency basis elements that span the column space M in our Φ_Λ matrix and n is the number of measurements that span the row space N as defined in the previous section. Thus m corresponds approximately to the bandwidth of the measurements and n corresponds to the number of measurements. This tradeoff has been looked a closely in many detection and estimation processes through such processes spectral kernel density estimation and cross validation. We now define coherence using a mixture of the preceding definitions with the normalized average coherence of elements in the support with:

$$\mu_{i,j \in \Lambda} \left(\tilde{m}, \frac{1}{n} \right) = 1/n \sum_{i,j \in \Lambda, i \neq j} \mu_{ij} \quad (9)$$

and the normalized average coherence with elements outside the support

$$\mu_{i,j \notin \Lambda} \left(\tilde{m}, \frac{1}{n} \right) = 1/n \sum_{i,j \notin \Lambda, i \neq j} \mu_{ij} \quad (10)$$

This can also be defined for atoms inside and outside the support. Now we can define the variance of our measurement process. Thus using the definition of average coherence let us formally define the expected

variance in terms of the average coherence as described by Marron [13]

$$C_{XX} = E(X\Omega X\Omega) = \frac{i_0\sigma^2}{n} = \sum_{i' \leq n, j' \leq \tilde{m}} (\mu_{i,j}\sigma)^2 = (\mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}(\tilde{m}, n)\sigma)^2 \quad (11)$$

We also define the expected mean \hat{m} and bias b_m according to Johnstone with

$$\hat{m} = E(m - \Omega b_m)^2 = n^{-1} \sum_{i > n, j > \tilde{m}} \theta_{i,j}^2 = (m - m\mu_{i,j \in \Lambda})^2 = (m\mu_{i,j \notin \Lambda}(\tilde{m}, n))^2 \quad (12)$$

where $\theta_{i,j} = X\Omega_{i,j}$. These descriptions of bias and variance are true if we do not have an oracle for our signal and noise distribution. With an oracle we can pre-specify our thresholds \tilde{m} and n . We will later use coherence as a means to set our desired \tilde{m} and n for a given bias and variance in our estimation and detection process. Thus our convergence can be parameterized by predicted covariance matrix C_{XX} and current estimated covariance matrix \tilde{C}_{XX} such that

$$\tilde{C}_{XX} = E \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{c}_{11} & \tilde{c}_{12} & \cdots & \tilde{c}_{1N} \\ \tilde{c}_{21} & \tilde{c}_{22} & \cdots & \tilde{c}_{2N} \\ \tilde{c}_{31} & \tilde{c}_{32} & \cdots & \tilde{c}_{3N} \end{bmatrix} \right\} \quad (13)$$

after finding our approximate eigen basis Ψ_Λ at each time step of the Orthogonal Matching pursuits process. Using a Frobenius Norm we can compute

$$\|C_{XX} - \tilde{C}_{XX}\|_2^2 = \sum_{m=1}^N |\lambda_m - \tilde{c}_{mm}|^2 + \|C_{XX}\|_2^2 - \sum_{m=1}^N |\tilde{c}_{mm}|^2 \quad (14)$$

The difference is known as the Hilbert Schmidt error [15,19] where λ_m are the eigenvalues of our diagonalized covariance matrix C_{XX} and \tilde{c}_{mm} are the diagonal coefficients for our approximate covariance matrix \tilde{C}_{XX} where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the L2 norm of our covariance matrices. The difference between desired and actual covariance matrix can characterize inaccuracies in the estimate of the signal and noise environment including signal distribution and bias in the estimate.

Candes and Tau [4] and Gribonval [12] have derived the conditions for general bounds of a sparse approximation algorithm using an L1 norm minimization process such as Matching Pursuits with the restricted isometry property as follows

$$(1 - \delta_\Lambda)\|X\|_2^2 \leq \|\Phi_\Lambda X\|_2^2 \leq (1 + \delta_\Lambda)\|X\|_2^2 \quad (15)$$

Where $C = \tilde{X}$ is the data matrix at our current number of measurements M and sample support N . and $\tilde{R}_{XX} = E\{\langle \tilde{X}, \tilde{X} \rangle\}$ is the associated covariance

matrix. Assuming Gaussian mixtures for signal and interference we have

$$\|\Omega_\Lambda\| \|C\|_2 = \mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}^2(m, n)\sigma^2 \quad (16)$$

and from the restricted isometry property we now have error bounds on the variance:

$$\sqrt{(1 - \delta_\Lambda)}\sigma \leq \mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}(\tilde{m}, n)\sigma \leq \sqrt{(1 + \delta_\Lambda)}\sigma \quad (17)$$

Similarly we have error bounds on the bias:

$$\sqrt{(1 - \delta_\Lambda)}m \leq \mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}(\tilde{m}, n)m \leq \sqrt{(1 + \delta_\Lambda)}m \quad (18)$$

Using the above limits from Donoho and Johnstone definition of empirical risk we can compute approximate risk bounds with this strategy such that empirical risk is computed such that

$$R_{emp}(\mu) = C_{XX} + \hat{m} = (\mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}(\tilde{m}, n)\sigma)^2 + (m\mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}(\tilde{m}, n))^2 \quad (19)$$

Instead however we will develop a risk estimate based on a maximum likelihood framework and incorporate these bounds directly into that framework.

IV. MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD AND RISK

We have seen the effect of the range of the variability of coherence on the sample covariance matrix. Now we will develop an analytic risk expression that incorporates the error in the covariance matrix into the estimation and detection process and use this to avoid exceeding our work case min max distribution error. If we now define a Gaussian likelihood function with our target present hypothesis H1 having normal distribution $N(m_1, \tilde{R}_{XX})$ with $m_1 = E\{X\}$ and our target absent hypothesis H0 having normal distribution $N(m_0, \tilde{R}_{XX})$ and $m_0 = E\{E\}$ then or likelihood ration $l(x)$ is:

$$l(x) = \exp((x - m_1)^T \mathbf{R}_{xx1}^{-1}(x - m_1) - (x - m_0)^T \mathbf{R}_{xx0}^{-1}(x - m_0)) \quad (20)$$

Taking the natural logarithm of both sides

$$\mathbf{L}(x) = ((x - m_1)^T \mathbf{R}_{xx1}^{-1}(x - m_1) - (x - m_0)^T \mathbf{R}_{xx0}^{-1}(x - m_0)) \quad (21)$$

If we assign our worst case min max distributions as follows, we can then parameterize the distribution of our likelihood functions. Thus if we assume $L(x)$ is a linear transformation of x we have. [18].

$$H_0 L(x) N\left(-\frac{d^2}{2}, d^2\right) \quad (22)$$

$$H_1 L(x) N\left(\frac{d^2}{2}, d^2\right) \quad (23)$$

Where d is defined

$$d^2 = \frac{\mu_{i,j \notin \Lambda}^2(\tilde{m}, n)}{\mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}^2(\tilde{m}, n)} (m_1 - m_0)^T \sigma^{-2} (m_1 - m_0) \quad (24)$$

Thus:

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_{i,j \notin \Lambda}^2(\tilde{m}, n)}{\mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}^2(\tilde{m}, n)} (m_1 - m_0)^T \sigma^{-2} (m_1 - m_0)}$$

d can roughly be thought of as our signal to interference ratio in our signal environment times our ratio of coherence. Lets parameterize our coherence ratio such that

$$d = \frac{\mu_{i,j \notin \Lambda}(\tilde{m}, n)}{\mu_{i,j \in \Lambda}(\tilde{m}, n)} R_{SE} = \mu_R R_{SE}$$

Our false alarm probability is

$$\alpha = 1 - Q(z) \quad (25)$$

where $Q(z) = \int_{-\infty}^z (2\pi)^{-1} \exp\{-x^2/2\} dx$.

Our miss probability is $1 - \beta$ where β

$$\beta = 1 - Q(z - d) \quad (26)$$

We can use this strategy to employ a hard thresholding rule for detection such that

$$r(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & L(x) \geq \eta \\ 0 & L(x) < \eta \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

We now can state where η is our threshold derived from our desire to minimize the maximum risk of the worst case distribution [18].

$$z = \frac{\eta + \frac{d^2}{2}}{d} \quad (28)$$

Donoho and Johnstone develop a soft thresholding rule based on Stein's unbiased risk estimator. Unlike this result, our result incorporates both bias and variance as parameterized by coherence. We will show how to develop a corresponding threshold rule in next section. We now define our risk with

$$\mathfrak{R}(p, r) = p_0 L_{01} \alpha + (1 - p_0) L_{10} (1 - \beta) \quad (29)$$

with L_{01} our respective loss when H1 is decided when H0 is true and L_{10} our loss when H0 is decided when H1 is true and p_0 the probability of H0.

But given that we can re-write our risk in terms of coherence using d we can parameterize our risk in terms our coherence and our spread of eigenvalues. Bounding μ_R we have

$$\frac{\sqrt{(1-\delta\lambda)}}{\sqrt{(1+\delta\lambda)}} \leq \mu_R \leq \frac{\sqrt{(1+\delta\lambda)}}{\sqrt{(1-\delta\lambda)}} \quad (30)$$

Assuming our risk is approximately a linear function of coherence our risk we have

$$\mathfrak{R}\left(\frac{\sqrt{(1-\delta\lambda)}}{\sqrt{(1+\delta\lambda)}}\right) \leq \mathfrak{R}(\mu_R) \leq \mathfrak{R}\left(\frac{\sqrt{(1+\delta\lambda)}}{\sqrt{(1-\delta\lambda)}}\right) \quad (31)$$

The Donoho and Johnstone risk function can potentially be analyzed for nonlinear distributions such as correlated signal and noise environments. For the purposes of this paper we will assume signal and noise signals are Gaussian distributed and then look at risk asymptotes.

V. THRESHOLDING, GRADIENT RISK, AND RESOURCE OPTIMIZATION

Going back to our earlier expression for risk we can develop some general guidelines for our thresholds in the estimation and detection processing. Looking at the probability of detection probability of false alarm ROC curves we can derive

$$L_{01} = cL_{10} \quad (32)$$

We can subdivide the regions of thresholds into three regions. We then look at the noise case where our threshold is much less than our signal to noise ratio as an example

$$\eta \ll d \quad (33)$$

We then have

$$z \sim \frac{d}{2} \quad (34)$$

We can now redefine risk with:

$$\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R) = p_0 L_{01}(1 - Q(z)) + (1 - p_0) L_{10}(Q(z - d)) \quad (35)$$

We will compute an example risk function for the trade space where $z \sim \frac{d}{2}$.

We can now create a Lagrange based optimization strategy to balance risk against resources. This form resembles the Lasso formulation with a regularization term μ_R and an error term $\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R)$. We have

$$\min(J(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_c))) = \min(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R) + \zeta \mu_R) \quad (36)$$

Approximating $Q(z) \cong \frac{1}{z\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp(-\frac{z^2}{2})$ we have

Creating the Newton step for the gradient descent we have

$$\mu_{R(n+1)} = \mu_{Rn} - \frac{J(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_{R(n)}))}{J'(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_{R(n)}))} \quad (37)$$

Where are n dimensional Jacobian is defined

$$J(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m}))) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{d(\mathfrak{R}_1(\mu_R(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m})))}{d\mathbf{n}} & \frac{d(\mathfrak{R}_1(\mu_R(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m})))}{d\mathbf{m}} \\ \frac{d(\mathfrak{R}_2(\mu_R(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m})))}{d\mathbf{n}} & \frac{d(\mathfrak{R}_2(\mu_R(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m})))}{d\mathbf{m}} \end{bmatrix}$$

The Jacobian can be maximizing the divergence of the set of target distributions from the set of noise distributions where i in $\mathfrak{R}_i(\mu_R(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m}))$ indicates different resource regimes for our risk expression. Looking at just the case where $z \sim \frac{d}{2}$ for constant m,n we have the following risk expression:

$$\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R) = p_0 L_{01} \left(1 - \frac{2}{\mu_{RE} R_{NE} \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\mu_R R_{NE})^2}{2}\right)\right) + (p_0 - 1) L_{10} \frac{2}{\mu_{RE} R_{NE} \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\mu_R R_{NE})^2}{2}\right) \quad (38)$$

The corresponding Jacobian is:

$$J(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R)) = (p_0 L_{01} + (1 - p_0) L_{10}) \frac{R_{NE}}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\mu_R R_{NE})^2}{2}\right) + \zeta \quad (39)$$

Setting the above expression to zero and setting our Lagrange multiplier ζ the corresponding value of $\mu_R^* \Rightarrow R_{minmax}(\mu_R^*)$

$$J'(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R)) = (p_0 L_{01} + (1 - p_0) L_{10}) \frac{R_{NE}^3}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} \mu_R \exp\left(-\frac{(\mu_R R_{NE})^2}{2}\right) \quad (42)$$

Essentially we are looking over a local geometric resource space parameterized by $\mu_R(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m})$. When this space changes globally we update with the Newton iteration. Because we have chosen Gaussian distributions this process is essentially a locally linear approximation process over some geometric representation of a Gaussian mixture model. We now state the basic algorithm for local linear approximation and update for global changes.

VI. DYNAMIC UPDATE OF RISK ASSESSMENT

The algorithm essentially uses a nonparametric regression approach to estimate the current distribution of the noise covariance matrix and we then bound the maximum risk of this approach with the uncertainty due to level of coherence in our measurements. This approach can incorporate other distributions but this is beyond the scope of this paper. Thus we have our complete algorithm with:

1. **Compute matching pursuits eigen-value approximation of the sample covariance matrix**
 \tilde{C}_{XX}

2. **Compute current detection and risk**
 $\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R)$

3. **Determine if**
 $\mathfrak{R}(\mu_R) \leq \mathfrak{R}_{minmax}(\mu_R)$

4. **If criteria 3 is not met, update the coherence as follows until it is met**

$$\mu_{R(n+1)} = \mu_{Rn} - \frac{J(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_{R(n)}))}{J'(\mathfrak{R}(\mu_{R(n)}))}$$

5. **Repeat from step 1**

VII. RESULTS

Figure 1 illustrates the bias vs. risk tradeoff. Thus by selecting our minimum risk for our bias variance tradeoff, we can compute our minmax lower bound by which to set our threshold for our wavelet coefficients \tilde{m} and our number of measurements n. As signal to noise changes we can adjust our coherence to stay in this minima.

Fig. 1 Empirical vs. Asymptotic Risk

Figure 2 shows how we can bound our risk based on our coherence such that for any given estimate of risk, we have an upper and lower bound of our certainty of that risk estimate based on the extremal eigenvalues of the covariance matrix. Also our minmax upper bound on the risk is determined by taking the derivative of our Lagrange resource equation and setting it equal to zero.

Fig. 2 Analytic Risk Bounds

VIII. CONCLUSION

We have shown that we can use coherence as a means of describing, bounding, and measuring risk in sensing scenarios, we can parameterize a high dimensional sensing environment and adaptively adjust to changing resource and measurement constraints. This strategy will enable us to effectively assess and manage uncertainty in systems that were two large and complex to manage previously.

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